

value varies with the nature of the ligand. Considering the temperature independent paramagnetism χ_p term as a measure of ligand field strength, the following order of ligand field strength has been established: salicylanil $>$ *m'*-nitrosalicylanil $>$ *p*-methylsalicylanil $>$ *p'*-nitrosalicylanil $>$ *p*-methylsalicylidene-2-iminopyridine $>$ salicylidene-2-iminopyridine.

An attempt has been made to examine the magnetic susceptibility values of isomeric substituted complexes. The values of χ_m suggest that introduction of substituent in salicylanil (in the salicylaldehyde ring as well as in the amine ring) in various positions causes an increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility value. Langevin's theory postulates that a decrease in the effective positive charge will result in an increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility. An order of increase in the susceptibility values as a result of substitution of different groups at isomeric positions is represented as follows: salicylanil $<$ *p*-methylsalicylanil; salicylanil $<$ *p'*-nitrosalicylanil $<$ *m'*-nitrosalicylanil; salicylidene-2-iminopyridine $<$ *p*-methylsalicylidene-2-iminopyridine.

According to French⁸, if the substituent is *ortho-para* directing, the *ortho* compound should have higher susceptibility than either *meta* or *para* compound, while when the substituent is *meta* directing, the compound has the highest susceptibility values than the other substituents. This difference is attributed to the presence of higher electron density at *ortho* position in compounds containing two-electron repelling groups *ortho* to each other, and in *meta* compound to a higher electron density at *meta* position when the two groups are *meta* to each other. The order indicates that the authors findings are in partial agreement with the above findings.

Percentage deviation and symmetry of the molecule: In the Schiff base complexes studied, coordination occurs through nitrogen⁹⁻¹² and that the bonds involved are of coordinate covalent type. These bonds are likely to cause contraction of the electronic orbits whereby value of $\sum \bar{r}^2$ of the molecule is decreased. Since diamagnetic susceptibility is a radical function, the decrease in the value of $\sum \bar{r}^2$ would lower the diamagnetic susceptibility of complex molecule. This view is supported by the negative deviations observed by the authors.

It is thus clear that the observed deviations from additivity may be due to the changes in the χ_d term of Van Vleck equation. Further, since the bond between component molecule is strong, it is likely to bring about a change in symmetry of the component molecule. χ_p term, which is also dependent on the symmetry of the molecule, is likely to be affected due to this type of bonding. Thus the observed deviation from additivity may be on account of the changes in terms χ_d and χ_p both. The deviation is therefore

the net result of the two opposing effects χ_d and χ_p having opposite signs. Since, the symmetry of complex formed may be entirely different from that of the constituent molecule, the change in the χ_p term would obviously be more significant.

It appears that the χ_p term is more significant in bringing about a change in the molar susceptibility of the complex. This term is dependent on the symmetry of the molecule; and hence, greater the symmetry of the molecule, the smaller will be its contribution to χ_m in the Van Vleck's equation. It is therefore expected that greater the symmetry of the molecule, smaller will be the deviation¹³ from additivity and vice-versa. Hence, all the complexes reported in this investigation appeared to be distorted.

References

1. M. PRASAD, S. S. DHARMATTI and S. V. GOKHALE, *Proc Indian Acad Sci, Sect A*, 1944, 20 224.
2. J. H. VAN VLECK, "The Theory of Electric and Magnetic Susceptibilities", Oxford University Press Oxford, 1932
3. S. FRED and O. KASPER, *J. Am Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 52, 4671
4. R. W. LAWRENCE, *J. Am Chem. Soc.*, 1994, 56, 776.
5. J. O. EISENSTEIN and M. H. L. PRYCE, *Proc. R. Soc., Ser. A*, 1955, 229, 20.
6. R. L. BELFORD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, 34, 318.
7. R. L. BELFORD and G. BELFORD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, 34, 1980
8. C. M. FRENCH, *Trans. Faraday Soc*, 1945, 41, 676.
9. N. S. BIRADAR and V. H. KULKARNI, *J. Less-Common Met.*, 1972, 26, 855.
10. N. S. BIRADAR, V. H. KULKARNI and N. N. SIRMOKADAM, *Karnatak Univ J. Sci.*, 1972, 17, 14
11. M. A. PUJAR and T. D. BHARAMAGODAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 462.
12. N. S. BIRADAR and A. L. LOCKER, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 11, 899.
13. J. V. NAVANGULE and M. G. DATAR, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1970

Thioarsenites of Less-common Metals. Electro-metric Investigations on the Composition of Uranyl Thioarsenites as a Function of pH

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THE composition of heavy metal arsenites precipitated by the addition of sodium arsenite solutions to heavy metal salts is governed mainly by pH. The investigation of these compounds is difficult because of the adsorption of arsenic oxide by metallic hydroxides; the conversion of orthoarsenite to pyro- and meta-arsenite takes place with great ease, and these dissolve in excess of alkali and acid¹. Consequently, analytical methods have failed to give a correct view of their composition.

Literature on thioarsenites is meagre. Some of the thioarsenites are probably best described as double sulphides, whereas others, e.g. Ag_3AsS_3 and TlAs_2S_3 , form anions². In view of insufficient and conflicting reports on the composition of thioarsenites and in absence of any reference on the formation of uranyl thioarsenites, it was considered worthwhile to carry out a systematic study on the formation and composition of uranyl thioarsenites. These studies carried out by electrometric techniques, have yielded more conclusive evidences on the composition of such compounds³⁻⁶.

Experimental

Uranyl acetate, arsenous oxide, sodium sulphide, ammonium sulphide and hydrochloric acid of extra-pure grade were used, and their solutions prepared in carbonate-free conductivity water. The standard solution of Na_3AsS_3 was prepared by digesting analysed sample of As_2S_3 in Na_2S solution of required strength³. Calculated amounts of HCl were then added to Na_3AsS_3 solutions in definite molecular proportions in order to vary the pH.

pH measurements were carried out using a Metrohm Herisau (Switzerland) pH meter and Schott Gerate glass combination electrode. The conductance of solutions was measured by employing a Metrohm conductometer. The solution (25 ml) was taken in the cell thermostated at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Using different concentrations of reactants, a series of pH and conductometric titrations were performed both by direct and reverse methods in aqueous and aqueous alcoholic media.

Results and Discussion

The solution of Na_3AsS_3 was prepared by digesting As_2S_3 in Na_2S solution in the molar ratio 1 : 3. The pH of the Na_3AsS_3 solution was found to be 12.6. HCl was mixed with Na_3AsS_3 in the molar ratio 1 : 1, whereupon $\text{Na}_4\text{As}_2\text{S}_5$ was formed and pH of the solution found to be 10.5.

Sodium orthothioarsenite titrations : A series of pH titrations were carried out using different concentrations of uranyl acetate (pH 4.1) and Na_3AsS_3 (pH 12.6). In direct titrations (Fig. 1, curve 1), when Na_3AsS_3 solution was used as titrant, a gradual decrease in pH value was observed till at the stoichiometric end-point (in case of a simple double decomposition reaction). A sharp downward jump in pH was observed at 3.2 molar ratio of $\text{UO}_2^{2+} : \text{AsS}_3^{3-}$, corresponding to the formation of the yellow precipitate of uranyl orthothioarsenite, $3\text{UO}_2\text{S}_2\text{As}_2\text{S}_3$ around pH 7.0. In case of reverse titrations (Fig. 1, curve 2), at first the pH gradually increased till in the vicinity of the end-point, when the last traces of uranyl got removed through precipitation; further addition of alkali thioarsenite

Fig. 1. Orthothioarsenite titrations: (1) and (3) 0.1 M $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{UO}_2$ added to 25 ml of 0.005 M Na_3AsS_3 , (2) and (4) 0.1 M Na_3AsS_3 added to 25 ml of 0.01 M $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{UO}_2$.

caused a marked jump in pH and resulting in precipitation of $3\text{UO}_2\text{S}_2\text{As}_2\text{S}_3$ according to the reaction,

Employing similar concentrations of the reactants, direct and reverse conductometric titrations (Fig. 1, curves 3 and 4) were carried out. Well defined breaks are obtained at the stoichiometric end-points, suggesting the formation of the same compound $3\text{UO}_2\text{S}_2\text{As}_2\text{S}_3$.

Sodium pyrothioarsenite titrations : In the direct pH-metric titrations of sodium pyrothioarsenite (pH 10.5) and uranyl acetate (pH 4.1) solutions (Fig. 2, curve 1), well defined breaks at the point corresponding to the formation of uranyl pyrothioarsenite were obtained around pH 5.5. The reverse titration curves (Fig 2, curve 2) also supported the formation of uranyl pyrothioarsenite according to the reaction,

Both direct and inverse conductometric titrations (Fig. 2, curves 3,4) showed the formation of the compound $2\text{UO}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{S}_3$.

Fig. 2. Pyrothioarsenite titrations: (1) and (3) 0.1 M $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{UO}_2$, added to 25 ml of 0.004 M $\text{Na}_4\text{As}_2\text{S}_5$, (2) and (4) 0.2 M $\text{Na}_4\text{As}_2\text{S}_5$, added to 25 ml of 0.003 M $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{UO}_2$.

Investigations on the formation of metal-thioarsenite were not successful because the compound formed was not stable and decomposed to a yellow precipitate of As_2S_3 .

Analytical study: The different uranyl arsenites were prepared by mixing stoichiometric amounts of uranyl acetate and the respective sodium thioarsenites. The precipitates obtained were washed several times with aqueous 10% (v/v) ethanolic solution and dried in a vacuum desiccator for 40 h. A known amount (2 g) of each of the above was digested with concentrated HNO_3 (15 ml) to dryness on a steam-bath. The treatment was repeated several times. The residue was dissolved in minimum quantity of HCl and then analysed⁷ for U and As. Sulphur in the uranyl thioarsenites was determined gravimetrically⁷. The compositions of the compounds established through the above analysis were found to be the same as that obtained by the electrometric methods.

The present electrometric and analytical investigations confirm the formation and precipitation of $3\text{UO}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{S}_3$ and $2\text{UO}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{S}_3$ around pH 7.0 and 5.5, respectively.

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References

1. F. EPHRAIM, "Textbook of Inorganic Chemistry", Gurney and Jackson, London, 1949, p. 745.
2. J. C. BAILAR, "Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry", Pergman Press, Oxford, 1973, Vol 11, p. 619.
3. S. PRASAD, *Anal. Asoc. Quim. Argentina*, in the press.
4. S. PRASAD, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1981, **59**, 563.
5. S. PRASAD, *An. Acad. Bras. Ciênc.*, 1982, **54**, 339.
6. S. PRASAD, *Rev. Latinoameric. Quim.*, 1984, **15**, 50.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1968, pp. 540, 367, 466.

Kinetics of Oxidation of Aliphatic Secondary Alcohols by *N*-Bromosaccharin

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N-BROMOSACCHARIN (NBSA) has been used sporadically as an oxidising agent in organic chemistry¹. While the mechanism of oxidation of organic compounds by *N*-bromosaccharin (NBS) has been fairly well established²⁻⁴, the reactions of NBSA have not been elucidated from the mechanistic point of view. We have therefore attempted to study the reactions of a variety of organic substrates with NBSA with a view to arrive at the mechanisms of the reactions and also to compare the reactivities of the two reagents NBS and NBSA. We report in this note the results on the kinetics of the oxidation of aliphatic secondary alcohols by NBSA.

Experimental

N-Bromosaccharin was prepared by the addition of bromine to the sodium salt of saccharin at 0°. All other reactants were commercial samples, purified by either distillation or crystallisation. Acetic acid (A.R.) was further purified⁵. The kinetics were followed under pseudo-unimolecular conditions (alcohol $\gg$ NBSA) by estimating the unreacted NBSA at various intervals of time by an iodometric procedure. The rate constants reported are the average of at least three kinetic runs and are reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of propan-2-ol, taken as a typical substrate, follows the rate law

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